

MODELS FOR IMPROVING THE PSYCHOLOGICAL TRAINING OF MILITARY PERSONNEL

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Abstract: *This article deals with the problem of psychological training of military personnel; the urgency of this problem is emphasized, since the current level of development of the Armed Forces of the states makes high demands on the professional training of military personnel. The author presents the positions of scientists who reveal the concept of psychological preparation, and also gives his own definition of this phenomenon. The article also contains a description of the types and forms of general, special and targeted psychological training aimed at creating the necessary resources for military personnel to perform tasks for their intended purpose.*

Key words: *psychological preparation, serviceman, readiness.*

Introduction. The problem of psychological training of military personnel has a long history, since from ancient times they tried to teach a soldier what should have been useful in a war: to restrain negative emotions, experiences, fear, pain, etc. political conviction, determination, risk, speed of reactions, etc. The emphasis was on the formation of moral and combat qualities (courage, resilience, readiness for self-sacrifice in the name of victory over the enemy, etc.).

The current level of development of the Armed Forces of the State Army also makes high demands on the military-professional, moral-political and psychological training of servicemen.

The means of armed struggle, methods of conducting combat operations are changing, the socio-political situation in the country is also rapidly changing, which increases the role of psychological factors in the training of personnel in maintaining the combat capability and readiness of troops.

The pioneers in studying the issues of psychological training of military personnel were M. I. Dyachenko, M. P. Korobeinikov, P. A. Korchemny, A. M. Stolyarenko, V. V. Sysoev, S. I. Sedin, N. F. Fedenko, successfully defended their doctoral dissertations on this issue. With their participation, fundamental works were

developed that reveal the psychological aspects of war, combat, combat and psychological training of troops [6].

For a long time, the issues of psychological preparation have been gaining sharpness: attention has been focused on emotional-volitional control, the development of specific mental functions, increasing mental stability, etc. In recent years, D. V. Gander, A. V. Girin have shown an active interest in the problem of psychological readiness, A. G. Karayani, M. I. Maryin, V. E. Petrov, A. M. Petrunin, A. D. Safonov, etc.

Scientists put forward proposals for improving psychological training: updating the content, methods and forms of training military personnel; it is recommended to pay special attention to the development of psychophysiological qualities that affect professional activities, behavior, interpersonal relationships [7].

They also note an increase in the importance of the human factor in solving combat training tasks, which, of course, requires new approaches to the psychological training of military personnel and to the professional training of officials who organize it [4].

Main part. An analysis of the scientific literature on the problem of psychological readiness for activity revealed different options for its definition: as an integral quality of a person, manifested in the general ability and readiness for independent, successful professional activity in a real socio-professional situation [1]; as a factor contributing to professional development [2]; as a holistic education, including interest, the need to achieve results; understanding of the tasks of professional activity, assessment of its significance; a sense of professional and social responsibility, confidence in success, self-control, focus on the task [3]. The psychological readiness for the activities of a serviceman is also determined by a combination of socio-psychological characteristics, including a high level of moral, political and psychological state.

Thus, we consider psychological readiness for professional activity as a complex, including:

- formed value-motivational sphere for military service;
- a sufficient level of functional state, optimal for the successful completion of tasks for the intended purpose;
- high and sufficient level of knowledge, skills and professionally important qualities.

Using the indicators of this complex, it is possible to assess the level of psychological readiness of a serviceman for activity. Psychological training can be carried out both individually and in a group format. This phenomenon has types:

general, special, target. General psychological training is carried out in all types of activities and is aimed at the formation of psychological readiness to perform the tasks of military service. There are forms of general psychological preparation [5,19]:

Psychological education (lectures, conversations, reports, printed visual materials, video films, etc.). Education is carried out through informing, displaying visual and video materials in order to convey information in order to form an algorithm or model of behavior in military personnel in extreme conditions of a combat situation, anticipation of various possible reactions to non-standard, combat stress factors; knowledge of ways to provide psychological assistance and assistance to colleagues.

Psychological hardening (modeling of hazard factors, tension during combat and physical training classes, simulators, simulations, etc.). Psychological hardening is carried out using obstacle courses, simulators, during which adaptation to extreme conditions of activity is carried out, various skills are developed, for example, making responsible decisions in risk situations. In the process of physical training, military personnel develop the necessary skills, for example, endurance, vestibular stability, dexterity, etc., with the help of special exercises and sports equipment. Psychotechnics (methods of volitional mobilization, mental relaxation, psychological support, assessment of the functional state, etc.). With the help of psychotechnics, a psychological impact is made on a serviceman, the purpose of which is to quickly mobilize, relax, change perception or behavior. Psycho tactics (sports and tactical games, computer games, simulators, rope courses, etc.) Special psychological training is aimed at the formation and development of special professionally important qualities, as well as psychological knowledge, skills and behavior in a combat situation (extreme situations), necessary to perform assigned tasks.

Special psychological training is carried out in the form of:

- training, individual and group overcoming of various types of obstacle courses (psychological, fire assault, reconnaissance trails, etc.) using simulation tools, technical means that generate combat conditions.
- special exercises, trainings, etc.

Target psychological training of personnel is carried out before the start of combat training operations, ensures the formation of psychological readiness to perform a specific combat mission.

At the present stage, targeted psychological training is aimed at training specific combat qualities (combat stress resistance) of all categories of servicemen.

Each type of psychological training is aimed at replenishing the positive psychological resource of military personnel, which is necessary to perform tasks for their intended purpose.

Conclusion

Thus, psychological training should become an effective tool for the formation of adaptability and psychological resistance to various stress factors of military activity; maintain high activity and morale of military personnel; demonstrate combat coherence, mutual assistance and mutual assistance of personnel on the basis of acquired professional knowledge, skills and abilities. The use of psychological training methods should keep pace with the times, take into account existing and advanced experience, trends in new means of modern warfare, therefore it is necessary to create banks of extreme (combat) situations with the development of methods for applying the right solutions and getting out of problem situations.

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